

**CREATION OF A DATABASE FOR THE SYSTEM PLATFORM OF
NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS****Sharopova Muhayyo**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10570899>**INTRODUCTION**

Based on the decisions, decrees and speeches of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the introduction of information, communication and modern pedagogical technologies into the educational system, today's advanced pedagogical technologies, information base resources and the increase in the need for software tools shows the urgency of its production and use in education. General concepts of database management systems, their types, classification, database models and forms of their standardization , the components of the languages working with the database and the technology of query organization, as well as information about the procedure for working with the knowledge base are presented. Students of academic lyceums and vocational colleges, as well as students of institutes and universities, are widely engaged in data processing on the basis of new information technologies using modern computers. Today, everyone who uses a computer can easily process texts using the WORD text editor, that is, format them in the desired form, print and make several copies. It is known to many people to do calculations in EXCEL and presentation processes in PowerPoint. Same as well as to internet pages information input from the HTML language for or from FrontPage use need you know Computer with depends and computer using very fast done increase possible has been so issues category they exist _ with each day and each in step it will happen . _ Such issues category data is called the base .

CREATION OF A DATABASE FOR THE SYSTEM PLATFORM OF NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS

Current at the time study process organize of reaching two main shape there is . It's online and offline is learning . This form to choose , or rather , study center in the activity which form superior to be , him organize reach and work principles depends

In our republic study centers organize from doing main the target is the student to young people selected field according to at school taking knowledge more

strengthening , and knowledge level is to increase . In society study centers user by subject deep level have to be help will give .

Of this importance that is , education centers the work time process of the student on time suitable in case choice , distance in terms of convenience of students to the talent suitable in case science choose opportunity , independent own on work opportunity and the most the main thing is short lifetime inside big to the result have to be opportunities will give .

Non-state study centers system platform for data base SQL data when creating base manage from the system was used and the following tables prepared :

1. Platform user first of all in the system register pass because it is necessary platform of the user data base if not formed , in the system there is of possibilities use ca n't Use it data in the base
2. Table 3 shows data base is formed .

id	f_name	f_surname	f_phone_number	f_login	f_password
1	Fakhriddin	Nuriddinov	*****	*****	*****
2	Hayitbek	Asrorov	*****	*****	*****
3	Mehroj	Amirkulov	*****	*****	*****
4	A star	Shodiyeva	*****	*****	*****
...	...	...	...	...	...

Table 3 . Use it in the system use for necessary information _ _ in himself _ storage opportunity giver table .

User information _ _ information _ _ in the base storage for the following the following API PHP programming in the language wrote :

```

<? php
    $host = "localhost";
    $user = " includei ";
    $ password = "Y106M8 etC[ z!T *";
    $ base = " includei_doctor_database ";
    header( "Access-Control-Allow-Origin: *");
    header( "Access-Control-Allow-Headers: *");
    header( "Content-Type: application/ json ");
    $ json_str = file_get_contents ( ' php ://input');
    $ json_obj = json_decode ( $ json_str );
    $ logink = $ json_obj ->login;
    $password = $ json_obj ->password;
    $ user_name = $ json_obj -> user_name ;

```



```

$user_phone = $ json_obj -> user_phone ;
$log= $ json_obj ->log;
$pass= $ json_obj ->pass;
$email= $ json_obj ->email;
if( $ logink = "*****" && $password = "*****") {
    $conn = mysqli_connect ( $host, $user, $ password , $ base );
    $ sql = "INSERT INTO registration ( user_name , user_phone ,
login, password, email )
    VALUES ('$ user_name ' , '$ user_phone ' , '$log', '$pas',
'$email')";
    if ( mysqli_query ( $ conn, $ sql )) {
        $success= array('success'=>'true');
        echo json_encode ($success);
    }
} else {
    $failure = array('success'=>'false');
    echo json_encode ($failure);
}
mysqli_close ($conn);
?>

```

3. Platform for study centers and they are about data was formed . Study centers about information of the platform data shown in Table 4 in the structure prepared .

id	m_name	m_address	m_phone_number	m_login	m_password	m_lon	m_lan
1	Include	Bukh.sh., A.Somiy k., 23 house	*****	***** **	*****	*****	*****
2	Web international	Bukh.sh., Piridastgir k., 128 house	***** **	***** ****	*****	*****	*****
3	ICity	Bukh.sh., I. Mominov street, 3 house	***** **	*****	*****	*****	*****
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...

Table 4 . Study _ _ centers necessary information _ _ in himself _ storage opportunity giver table .

4. Platform for study in the centers study of professors who give data base was formed . Study in the centers study of professors who give about information of the platform data shown in Table 5 in the structure prepared .

id	id_center	f_teacher_name	f_teacher_surname	f_teacher_father's_name
1	1	Alibek	Shodmonov	Nasullayevitch
2	1	Recreation	Gaibullayev	Otabek son
3	1	Able to	Aslanov	Ziyadullayevich
...	...	...	...	...

Table 5 . Study _ _ in the centers organization giving professor - o ' teachers information _ _ in himself _ storage opportunity giver table .

5. Platform study centers listeners for organize done sciences of the complex data base was formed . Study in the centers study to be given sciences about information of the platform data shown in Table 6 in the structure prepared .

id	id_center	t_science_name
1	1	Web programming
2	1	Computer literacy
3	1	3d modeling
...	...	...

Table 6 . Study _ _ in the centers organize done sciences complex information _ _ in himself _ storage opportunity giver table .

6. Platform study centers users for organize done of sciences graph data base was formed . Study in the centers study to be given sciences about information of the platform data shown in Table 7 in the structure prepared .

id	id_center	t_science_id	t_teacher_id	t_day_of_the_week	t_time
1	1	2	3	Monday , Thursday	13:00
2	1	1	1	Tuesday , Friday	13:00
3	1	3	2	Wednesday , Saturday	13:00

...	...	...	...	...	...
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Table 7 . Study __ in the centers organize done of sciences graph information __ base in himself _ storage opportunity giver table .

7. Platform of users study in the centers organize done online registration for subjects done increase for intended data base was formed . Users study in the centers organize done online registration for subjects information of the platform data shown in Table 8 in the structure prepared .

id	id_science	id_t	if_f
1	2	1	1
...	...	...	...

Table 8 . Study __ in the centers organize done to the sciences online from registration tooth __ information __ base in himself _ storage opportunity giver table

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